

UNRAVELING THE BEHAVIORAL PATHWAYS: FINANCIAL KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE AS DETERMINANTS OF FINANCIAL SATISFACTION AMONG MARKET INVESTORS

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Abstract

Purpose: This study aims to examine the association between financial knowledge and financial attitude on the financial satisfaction of market investors, serving the mediating role of investor behavior.

Design/method: In this study, 300 samples from Pakistan's market are used. The data is collected with feedback and questions. Two kinds of analysis are done, the outer and the inner model.

Results: The results of this study are interconnected with the prior research that showed a significant relationship between financial knowledge and financial attitude on financial satisfaction.

Implication: This study is done with the questionnaire method and data is collected within a specific area. Additionally, this research is investigated in other areas.

Practical Implications: This work has significant value for people who are practical in the field. Additionally, it is also supportive for investors, because it exposes the numerous factors that are affecting their satisfaction.

Uniqueness: Many scholars employ studies to evaluate the validity of tools in a particular scenario and example. This research exposed the findings performed different validations and constructed the financial contentment in Pakistan is rigorously validated.

INTRODUCTION

Satisfaction can be understood as an evaluation of how well an individual is achieving economic well-being, as noted by Hira and Mugenda (1998). According to Joo (2008), financial satisfaction reflects a person's monetary situation; when individuals experience a positive financial condition, they often feel secure and unburdened. Lyubomirsky (2005) emphasizes that certain behaviors can

significantly enhance overall satisfaction. This connection between behavior and satisfaction also applies to financial matters, as financial behaviors can influence an individual's level of financial satisfaction. Joo and Grable (2004) demonstrated that financial behavior affects financial satisfaction, a concept supported by later studies (Godwin, 1984; Godwin & Carroll, 1986; Mugenda, Hira, &

Fanslow, 1990). Researchers such as Xiao et al. (2009) and Joo (2008) have highlighted that financial behavior is a crucial factor in determining personal financial satisfaction.

Financial behavior refers to the actions and decisions involved in managing finances, including investing, borrowing, saving, and engaging in money market activities (Xiao, 2008; Capuano & Ramsay, 2011). Within capital markets, investor behavior represents a specific aspect of financial behaviour. Planned behavior theory is useful for analyzing and understanding financial decision-making and actions. It suggests that individuals engage in certain behaviors based on their perceived capabilities and the expected outcomes of those actions. Mustikasari (2007) notes that when individuals follow through with planned financial actions, they derive satisfaction from the results of their efforts. This framework establishes a causal link between financial literacy, behavior, and satisfaction.

Strong financial literacy is essential for making informed financial decisions, which in turn leads to financial satisfaction. According to Joo (2008), financial knowledge is a key component of financial well-being, alongside behavior and satisfaction. Financial literacy encompasses an understanding of concepts such as saving, investing, credit, and taxation, as noted by Bowen (2002). This knowledge affects financial behavior, which subsequently influences overall satisfaction. Worthy et al. (2010) and Xiao et al. (2009) argue that financial education encourages positive financial behavior, ultimately enhancing quality of life.

Financial attitudes, which are shaped by beliefs and perceptions, play a significant role in financial satisfaction. According to Halim and Astuti (2015), financial attitude refers to an individual's judgments, opinions, and mindset regarding finances. Having a positive attitude towards saving, investing, and financial planning contributes to long-term financial health and satisfaction. These attitudes often develop from personal financial experiences and the value individuals assign to money. Research by Arifin (2018) and others has examined how financial knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors interact to influence financial satisfaction. Arifin's findings suggest that financial knowledge and attitudes have a positive impact on the financial satisfaction with the

financial behaviour helping the research as a mediator.

The connection among financial knowledge, socialization, and satisfaction has been a focus of various studies. For example, Saurabh and Nandan (2018) found that financial risk attitudes and behaviors act as mediators in the relationship between financial socialization, knowledge, and satisfaction. They suggested that further research should examine additional factors, like solvency and financial stressors. Likewise, Herawati et al. (2018) demonstrated that financial literacy, self-efficacy, and socioeconomic status play significant roles in influencing financial behavior, underscoring the necessity to explore further determinants of financial behavior.

Research by Ahmed et al. (2017) and Coşkuner (2016) has highlighted the important roles of financial behavior in influencing overall satisfaction. Ahmed's study demonstrated a positive relationship between financial literacy and satisfaction, indicating that this relationship is mediated by financial behavior. Coşkuner emphasized that both financial knowledge and behavior significantly affect satisfaction and suggested that further research utilizing longitudinal methods is necessary to uncover causal relationships. Additionally, Christian Yap (2016) pointed out the impact of financial attitudes and management behaviors on satisfaction, advocating for further exploration of attitude-related factors.

This study aims to address the underexplored relationship between financial knowledge, financial attitudes, and financial satisfaction, with financial behavior acting as a mediating variable. Previous research has not adequately investigated how these variables interact, particularly in the context of capital market investors. By focusing on these dynamics, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence financial satisfaction.

Moreover, the research offers practical implications for policymakers, educators, and investors. Understanding the role of investment ethics and financial behavior in shaping satisfaction can help in designing policies that promote financial literacy and ethical investment practices. Additionally, insights from this study could support investors in forming

knowledgeable decisions and improving their financial well-being.

In conclusion, this study builds upon the theoretical foundation of the theory of planned behavior to explore the complex relationships between financial knowledge, financial attitudes, and financial satisfaction. By addressing the identified research gaps, it aims to contribute to the academic discourse on behavioral finance and provide actionable insights for stakeholders in the financial sector.

Literature Review

Ajzen (1980) stated that satisfaction can be understood through the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). According to this theory, behavior is driven by the intention to either perform or refrain from a specific action. The intention to engage in or avoid a behavior is influenced by two fundamental attitudes: the beliefs about the behavior and the emotional norms associated with those beliefs. These beliefs are related to the awareness of the behavior, as examined by Mustikasari (2007). Through this process, individuals are motivated to act. Once a planned action is executed, satisfaction arises from the behavior.

2.1 Financial satisfaction

Financial satisfaction refers to a state of happiness and well-being regarding one's financial situation, as expressed by Zimmerman (1995). It indicates that an individual's financial condition is satisfactory, and that they are generally happy, which alleviates anxiety related to their financial circumstances, as defined by Joo (2008). According to Hira and Mugenda (1998), financial satisfaction involves a personal assessment of one's financial situation. Ali et al. (2015) further characterize financial satisfaction by the individual's present financial condition.

Draughn et al. (1994) identify three components of financial satisfaction: (a) financial capability, which relates to the ability of income to meet financial obligations; (b) perceived financial well-being, an emotional assessment of financial adequacy; and (c) satisfaction with one's current situation, which reflects a person's ability to fulfill their financial needs. Lown and Ju (1992) explain that financial satisfaction is measured by the gap between an individual's desires and their actual financial

condition. The smaller the gap between financial aspirations and reality, the higher the level of financial satisfaction.

Income and wealth are two financial circumstances that influence financial satisfaction and subjective perceptions of financial needs, as suggested by Plagnol (2011). Hira and Mugenda (1999) identify the fundamental factors that affect financial satisfaction, which include (a) savings, (b) debt, (c) current financial situation, (d) ability to meet long-run needs, (e) emergency funds, and (f) management skills. To assess financial satisfaction researchers like Toscano et al. (2006), Joo and Grable (2004), and Xiao et al. (2014) have used the single question: "How satisfied are you with your current financial condition?"

2.2 Investor Behavior

Xiao (2008) suggests that this behaviour reflects human behaviour interconnected with financial management. Hogarth et al. (2003) examine investor behaviour as three main elements: (1) saving, (2) investment, and (3) cash flow management. The connection between financial management tasks and investor behavior is suggested by Ida and Dwinta (2010). For example, effective financial administration includes in examining the funding and handling debt within a manageable time.

Hira and Mugenda (1999) supposed that investor behavior is shaped by individual attitudes and actions related to financial management. In this work spending and saving are used as benchmarks for evaluating investor behavior. Nababan et al. (2012) highlight that individual investor behavior involves how one treats, manages, and utilizes existing resources.

Investor behavior can be measured through several items, including (a) expenditure, (b) bill payment, (c) financial planning, (d) providing for oneself and one's family, and (e) saving. These aspects have been examined Grable et al. (2009), Kholilah and Iramani (2013), Perry and Morris (2005), and Ida and Cinthia (2010).

2.3 Financial knowledge

According to Halim and Astuti (2015), financial knowledge is defined as the capacity to know, assess, and manage finances to make knowledgeable

decisions and avoid financial difficulties. Ida and Dwinta (2010) expressed that gaining financial knowledge needs to develop financial skills learning to utilize financial tools, for example, choosing investments, choosing an insurance plan and making a budget. Danes et al. (1999) and Keller and Staelin (1987) written-up that financial knowledge can be acquired through courses, training, education, and non-formal education, including formal schooling and education. Numerous keys are assessed to estimate financial knowledge, like (a) investment, (b) interest rates, credit and financial charges, (c) credit reports, (d) credit levels and credit information, and (e) financial management, Perry and Morris (2005). Grable et al. (2009) and Ida and Cinthia (2010) also support these indicators.

2.4 Financial attitude

According to Eagle, attitude is a psychological propensity primarily communicated as either liked or disliked (Chaiken, 1993). Attitudes lead to behavior, which refers to the level of measurement that either supports or does not support the conduct to be executed (Ajzen, 1991). Attitudes encompass feelings, thoughts, and individual tendencies regarding specific aspects that can be clearly categorized as agreeable or non-agreeable, including objects, individuals, and events (Rajna et al., 2011). When it comes to finances, attitudes involve thoughts, assessments, and opinions. Rajna et al. (2011) propose measuring financial attitudes through 11 statements, which are given below:

1. Rising and keeping a constant savings habit is crucial for attaining financial stability and meeting long-term objectives.
2. It is necessary to create clear financial goals to guide and prioritize spending decisions.
3. Creating and adhering to a written-up budget is a basic step toward effective financial management.
4. every individual must take personal responsibility for ensuring their financial well-being.
5. Saving is not important.
6. As long as I make my monthly payments, I don't need to worry about how long it will take to pay off my debt.
7. It is important to be aware of and monitor your savings to ensure financial constancy and attain your long-term objectives.

8. Financial planning for retirement is essential to ensure stability during old age.

9. It is important to plan for potential disability income.

10. make sure that in the future for successful management, insurance is important for reasonable risks.

11. For financial success, it is mandatory to think about your finances in the next 5 to 10 years.

Methodology

This study employs an explanatory investigation to define the association between various variables and to conclude through hypothesis testing. The focus of this research is on the financial satisfaction of capital market investors. The key items examined in this study include financial knowledge, financial attitude, investor behavior, and financial satisfaction.

Primary data for this study was collected through an online questionnaire, which was distributed via email and other platforms. A total of 300 responses were gathered from capital market investors in Islamabad and Rawalpindi, Pakistan. The questionnaires were sent to investors who had completed more than one transaction and were active participants in the market.

The data analysis technique used in this research is Smart PLS, which involves two phases to measure the fit of the research model (Ghozali, 2014). These phases consist of the outer model and the inner model. The validity and reliability of the data are assessed through these models, with the structural model illustrating the relationships among financial knowledge, financial attitude, and financial satisfaction, with investor behavior acting as an intervening variable.

Financial knowledge is evaluated using five indicators, while financial attitude is assessed through eleven indicators. Investor behavior is measured with five indicators, and financial satisfaction is determined using six indicators. The outer model test is conducted to verify the validity and reliability of these variables. The validity test includes both convergent validity and discriminant validity (Ghozali, 2014).

4. Analysis and Result

According to Hair (2014), there are several methods to assess convergent validity, discriminant validity, and internal consistency reliability using the outer model of SmartPLS.

Convergent validity refers to the degree to which measurements of the same concept are associated with one another. In contrast, discriminant validity indicates that a construct is distinctly different from other factors being measured. Finally, composite reliability pertains to the reliability based on the relationships among the observed variables.

4.1 Convergent validity

The following steps outline how to identify convergent validity through the outer model (Measurement Model) using loading factors. According to Chin (1998) and Ghozali (2014), a loading value range of 0.6 to 0.7 serves as a basic benchmark for initial studies. In this research, a loading value of 0.7 was used as the threshold. During the analysis, any indicators with loading values below 0.7 would typically be removed. However, in this case, no indicators were eliminated, as all indicators had loading values above 0.7.

Table No.1 Outer loadings (Measurement Model)

Financial knowledge		Financial Attitude		Investor Behavior		Financial Satisfaction	
Initials	Modify	Initials	Modify	Initials	Modify	Initials	Modify
0.777	0.777	0.782	0.782	0.824	0.824	0.855	0.855
0.820	0.815	0.761	0.756	0.883	0.778	0.875	0.870
0.855	0.856	0.794	0.795	0.843	0.844	0.899	0.890
0.743	0.750	0.760	0.767	0.830	0.837	0.825	0.832
0.758	0.762	0.741	0.745	0.845	0.849	0.861	0.865
		0.812	0.810			0.836	0.834
		0.847	0.845				
		0.856	0.856				
		0.872	0.876				
		0.780	0.778				
		0.781	0.799				

After analysis, the results indicate that the outer model's values, or the associations among factors and variables, are acceptable because their convergent validity is met. Additionally, many indicators remain valid, as shown in Table 1, and their loading factors are above 0.70. In the modified model, all indicators have loading factors above 0.70, using the outer loading method (Measurement Model). No values are missing in this table, which means that all constructs fully satisfy the requirement of having loading factors above 0.70.

According to Hair (2014), convergent validity is considered high when the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is above 0.50, indicating that the model should be classified as exhibiting high convergent validity. Another method used in the measurement model involves eliminating loading factors that are below 0.50, which is known as AVE.

Table 2: Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Factors	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Financial Knowledge	0.503
Financial Attitude	0.513
Investor Behavior	0.574
Financial Satisfaction	0.513

Based on the average variance extracted method, the following conclusions were drawn:

The average for financial knowledge is 0.503 financial attitude is 0.513, the research intervening variable is 0.574, and the financial satisfaction (dep variable) is 0.513. this serves as the second method to establish the convergent validity in this study.

4.2 Discriminant Validity

To assess discriminant validity, cross-loading will be used as a criterion. A model is considered to have good discriminant validity if the cross-loading results demonstrate that each construct’s indicators have significantly higher values than the indicators of the

other constructs, as noted by Hair (2014). The cross-loading results, shown in Table 3 above, indicate that all indicators are valid and acceptable because each construct’s indicators have higher values compared to the indicators of other constructs.

Table 3: Cross Loading

S.NO	Financial Knowledge	Financial Attitude	Financial Satisfaction	Investor Behavior
FK 1	0.777	0.460	0.489	0.523
FK 2	0.815	0.450	0.480	0.443
FK 3	0.856	0.520	0.496	0.445
FK 4	0.750	0.489	0.521	0.566
FK 5	0.762	0.399	0.493	0.494
FA 1	0.333	0.782	0.398	0.498
FA 2	0.341	0.756	0.378	0.511
FA 3	0.351	0.795	0.431	0.543
FA 4	0.363	0.767	0.423	0.574
FA 5	0.335	0.745	0.416	0.548
FA 6	0.378	0.810	0.421	0.592
FA 7	0.411	0.845	0.420	0.582
FA 8	0.435	0.856	0.388	0.589
FA 9	0.425	0.876	0.400	0.495
FA 10	0.436	0.778	0.539	0.470
FA 11	0.399	0.799	0.439	0.570
FS 1	0.317	0.378	0.855	0.533
FS 2	0.340	0.431	0.870	0.390
FS 3	0.453	0.410	0.890	0.391
FS 4	0.432	0.319	0.832	0.412
FS 5	0.370	0.427	0.865	0.512
FS 6	0.392	0.381	0.834	0.438
IB 1	0.436	0.386	0.339	0.824
IB 2	0.471	0.446	0.393	0.778
IB 3	0.410	0.458	0.489	0.844
IB 4	0.397	0.496	0.318	0.837
IB 5	0.418	0.349	0.340	0.849

4.3 Composite Reliability

In this research paper, the term "mean" in exploratory research refers to composite reliability values, which range from 0.60 to 0.70, as noted by

Hair (2014). A construct is considered to have high reliability if it falls within the minimum threshold of 0.60. Therefore, in Table 4, the standards for composite reliability are outlined as follows:

Table 4: Cronbach’s Alpha and Composite Reliability

Variable	Cronbach’s Alpha	Composite Reliability
Financial Knowledge	0.932	0.932
Financial Attitude	0.846	0.850
Financial Satisfaction	0.811	0.845
Investor Behaviour	0.733	0.872

After analyzing the Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability presented in Table 3, we can conclude that each construct meets reliable criteria, as all constructs have values greater than 0.70. This indicates that the independent variables—namely the Ethics of Investment, Financial Knowledge, and Financial Attitude—are reliably associated with Financial Behavior, which in turn has a positive correlation with Financial Satisfaction. Each variable in this model exceeds the specified threshold for reliability. Furthermore, in the measurement model (outer model), all conditions are satisfied,

demonstrating convergent validity, discriminant validity, as well as acceptable Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability values.

4.4 (Inner Model) Structural Model Testing

To classify the associations among constructs, the inner model (structural model) is utilized. This model helps to determine the R-squared value and significance of the research findings. In this paper, the inner model is evaluated using the R-squared value along with t-tests and significance related to the path parameter coefficients.

Figure 1. Structural Model of Study

After evaluating the model with Smart-PLS, we begin by examining the R-square values for each dependent

variable. The results of the R-square values are presented in Table 5 using the Smart-PLS method.

Table 5: R-Square Value

Variable	R- Square
Financial Knowledge	
Financial Attitude	
Investor Behaviour	0.879
Financial Satisfaction	0.924

In the structural model, as shown in Table 1, the R-squared assessment for investor behavior variables is 0.879. This indicates that 87.9% of the variations in investor behavior can be attributed to ethical variables in investing, while the remaining 12.1% is influenced by other factors outside the scope of the study.

Furthermore, the R-squared value for the financial satisfaction variable is 0.924. This conclusion suggests that 92.4% of the factors affecting financial satisfaction can be attributed to ethical variables in

investing and investor behavior, with the remaining 7.6% affected by other external variables not included in the analysis.

Hypothesis testing

For hypothesis testing, the output path coefficient value must be calculated. Therefore, Table 6 presents the evaluation output of the inner model or structural model testing.

Table 6: Hypothesis Test Outcomes

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Significance level
FK->FS	0.517	6.135	0.000	***
FA->FS	0.560	7.175	0.000	***
FK->IB	0.540	6.543	0.000	***
FA->IB	0.565	7.721	0.000	***
IB->FS	0.541	6.764	0.000	***
FK->IB->FS	0.544	6.696	0.000	***
FA->IB->FS	0.679	13.543	0.000	***

NS= Insignificance

*** = p < 0.01

*** = p < 0.05

In this study, each hypothesis tested in the PLS numerical test is associated with a specific model. The bootstrap technique has been employed to minimize data issues and abnormalities. Below are the results of the PLS analysis with bootstrapping:

Hypothesis 1: This hypothesis states that financial knowledge has a significant effect on financial satisfaction. The coefficient path value is 0.517, with a t-value of 6.135, indicating that financial knowledge positively affects financial satisfaction. This value exceeds the t-statistic threshold of 1.96, leading to the acceptance of Hypothesis 1.

Hypothesis 2: This hypothesis posits that financial attitude significantly influences financial satisfaction.

The coefficient path value is 0.560, with a t-value of 7.175, clearly demonstrating that financial attitude has a significant effect on financial satisfaction. Since this value is also greater than the rule value of 1.96, Hypothesis 2 is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: This hypothesis states that financial knowledge significantly impacts financial behavior. The coefficient path value is 0.540, with a t-value of 6.543, showing that financial knowledge significantly influences investor behavior. As this value exceeds the t-statistic threshold of 1.96, Hypothesis 3 is accepted.

Hypothesis 4: This hypothesis indicates that financial attitude has a significant effect on investor behavior. The coefficient path value is 0.565, with a t-value of 7.721, which clearly demonstrates that financial attitude positively affects investor behavior.

Given that this t-statistic is greater than 1.96, Hypothesis 4 is accepted.

Hypothesis 5: This hypothesis illustrates that financial behavior has a significant effect on financial satisfaction. The coefficient path value is 0.541, with a t-value of 6.764, which surpasses the threshold of 1.96. Thus, Hypothesis 5 is accepted.

Hypothesis 6: This hypothesis articulates that financial knowledge positively affects financial fulfillment through investor behavior. The coefficient path value is 0.544, with a t-value of 6.696, indicating a significant positive effect of financial knowledge on financial satisfaction through financial behavior. Since this value is greater than 1.96, Hypothesis 6 is accepted.

Hypothesis 7: This hypothesis states that financial attitude positively impacts financial satisfaction through investor behavior. The coefficient path value is 0.679, with a t-value of 13.543, clearly showing the significant positive effect of financial attitude on financial satisfaction via investor behavior. Given that this value exceeds 1.96, Hypothesis 7 is accepted.

Discussion

The connection between financial knowledge and financial satisfaction, with investor behavior as an intervening variable, has a positive effect. This supports Hypothesis 1. Additionally, the relationship between financial attitude and financial satisfaction, with financial investor behavior acting as a mediating variable, has a significant effect. This aligns with Hypothesis 2. The discussion should focus on these key variables, as the study is centered around hypothesis testing.

5.1.1 The effect of financial knowledge towards financial satisfaction with investor behavior as intervening variable

In conclusion, the results indicate that financial knowledge has a positive effect on financial behavior. Individuals who are knowledgeable about various financial concepts, such as interest rates, credit terms, credit card bills, and effective financial management and investment strategies, tend to exhibit better financial behavior. Similarly, aspects such as paying

bills on time, financial planning, meeting personal needs, obtaining insurance, and saving also contribute positively.

The rationale is that financial knowledge is often built through higher education. This study further demonstrates that positive financial behavior significantly influences financial satisfaction. In other words, good financial behavior in response to one's financial situation leads to greater financial satisfaction.

5.1.2 The effect of financial attitude towards financial satisfaction with investor behavior as an intervening variable

In the relationship between financial attitude and financial satisfaction, financial behavior plays a key role as an intervening variable. Financial attitude has a positive effect on financial satisfaction through financial behavior. A primary factor influencing financial attitude is the routine of saving. Therefore, increasing financial satisfaction is closely linked to the practice of regular saving.

Overall financial satisfaction relies on effective financial management, as planning is the most crucial factor for achieving financial contentment. Individuals making investments should adopt these strategies to meet their needs through substantial savings. This technique is often employed in investment strategies focusing on savings as a means to secure a safe future for immediate needs.

All findings in this research are supported by previous studies. For instance, Chandra and Memarista (2005) found a significant positive connection between financial attitude and financial satisfaction. Joo and Grable (2004) similarly defined a significant positive relationship between these two elements. Numerous other researchers, including Xiao et al. (2006, 2009), Halim and Astuti (2015), and Coskuner (2016), have also supported these statements. Additionally, financial behavior has been identified as a mediating variable that influences the relationship between financial attitudes and financial satisfaction.

Conclusions

This research confirms that financial behavior significantly impacts financial satisfaction among capital market investors in Islamabad and Rawalpindi. Financial satisfaction is influenced by

financial knowledge, behavior, and attitude, aligning with the theory of planned behavior. Individuals must make mindful financial decisions, as these factors collectively shape their overall satisfaction.

Financial knowledge enhances an individual's ability to manage finances, understand financial challenges, and make informed decisions. It encompasses skills related to managing credit, understanding interest rates, planning savings, and making future investments. Savings, which are crucial for investments, are driven by an individual's financial attitude, reflecting their thoughts, opinions, and approach to financial management.

The findings of this study indicate that financial satisfaction is influenced by financial behavior, as investors often base their decisions on risk tolerance and expected returns. Financial knowledge and attitude are key determinants in shaping satisfaction, enabling individuals to effectively navigate financial decisions.

Financial attitude plays a crucial role in fostering financial satisfaction by encouraging routine savings. A positive financial attitude helps individuals make sound decisions, manage risks, and prepare for future investments. Savings, closely tied to financial attitudes, are essential for achieving financial goals.

This research concludes that financial behavior plays a central role in improving financial satisfaction among investors. Additionally, financial behavior mediates the relationship between financial knowledge and financial satisfaction, highlighting its importance in translating financial awareness into tangible outcomes. Furthermore, financial attitude significantly influences financial satisfaction, with financial behavior acting as an intervening variable, emphasizing the need for a holistic approach to financial well-being. In summary, financial satisfaction increases when individuals possess strong financial behavior, knowledge, and attitudes. Financial knowledge empowers individuals to manage their finances effectively, develop essential skills, and utilize financial tools for planning savings, investments, and insurance. Finally, financial attitude significantly impacts financial satisfaction by shaping how individuals think and feel about managing their finances. A positive attitude helps individuals face risks, make informed decisions, and achieve their financial goals. Financial behavior

integrates knowledge and attitude, enabling effective decision-making and contributing to overall financial satisfaction. Policymakers should promote financial literacy programs to enhance positive financial attitudes and behaviors, leading to greater financial satisfaction.

Future Recommendations

Following the analysis and results of this research, several recommendations for further study have been developed:

1. Additional research should explore other factors that may influence investor behavior and financial satisfaction.
2. Future studies could examine respondents from different cities that better represent the range of financial investment methods and techniques.
3. The sample size should be increased to more accurately reflect the broader Pakistani population.

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